

Studies on Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Iron(II) with α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamide, α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido 2'-thiazole and α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido-4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidine

S. V. PATEL, J. N. VASAVADA, N. Y. NAGAR and G. B. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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Metal complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Fe^{II} with α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamide, α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido 2'-thiazole, and α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido-4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidine have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, tga, uv, visible and ir spectral studies and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The structures of the complexes have been proposed. The stepwise stability constants of the complexes have also been determined.

THE ligands, α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamide (SNCHB), α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido-2'-thiazole (STCHB), and α -phenyl-4-(5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy benzal amino)benzene sulphonamido-4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidine (SDCHB) have drug property as well as chelating property. In view of their medicinal properties synthesis, structural and solution studies of their complexes with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Fe^{II} have been undertaken and the results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Chlorides and nitrates of copper, nickel and cobalt, and ferrous ammonium sulphate of B.D.H. AnalaR grade were used for the synthesis of metal complexes.

Synthesis of ligands: The ligands SNCHB, STCHB and SDCHB were synthesised¹ by condensing 5-chloro-2-hydroxy benzophenone with sulphanimide, sulpha thiazole and sulpha dimedene, respectively. The ketone and sulpha drugs were mixed in 1:1 molar ratio in ethanol and refluxed for 3-4 h after adding some sodium acetate and a few drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was poured in water and Schiff bases thus obtained were filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol. These were characterized by elemental analysis.

Preparation of metal complexes: The complexes were synthesised by refluxing ethanolic solutions of ligand and metal salt for 2 h. In the synthesis of copper, nickel and cobalt complexes excess of ammonium hydroxide was added in the reaction mixture, whereas in the case of iron complexes pH 6.0-7.0 was maintained by adding ammonium hydroxide and acetic acid. The complexes obtained were purified and crystallized from chloroform and were analysed (Table 1).

Physical measurements: Electrical conductances were measured using Philips conductometer and dip type cell, calibrated with KCl solution. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance calibrated with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$, diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants and the magnetic moments recorded (Table 1). IR spectra were obtained using KBr discs. Electronic spectra were recorded on Toshniwal spectrometer using matched silica cells.

pH-metric measurements: For the determination of stepwise stability constants an expanded scale Systronic pH meter with accuracy ± 0.02 units was employed. All experiments were carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen and the temperature was maintained constant using thermostat. The following sets were prepared for titrations.

* Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL STUDY AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF SCHIFF BASES AND METAL CHELATES

Formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	O	H	N	S	
$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl$	—	59.10 (59.14)	3.61 (3.68)	7.22 (7.26)	8.28 (8.30)	D
$Cu(C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl)_2$	7.58 (7.51)	54.62 (54.64)	3.31 (3.36)	5.02 (5.03)	7.66 (7.67)	2.05
$Ni(C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl)_2$	7.08 (7.08)	54.93 (54.96)	3.34 (3.37)	5.04 (5.06)	7.65 (7.71)	D
$Co(C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl)_2$	7.04 (7.10)	54.90 (54.95)	3.36 (3.37)	5.01 (5.06)	7.67 (7.71)	2.33
$Fe(C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2SCl.H_2O)_2$	6.44 (6.49)	52.80 (52.85)	3.68 (3.71)	6.45 (6.49)	7.41 (7.42)	D
$C_{22}H_{22}O_4N_4SCl$	—	61.01 (61.03)	4.23 (4.27)	11.34 (11.39)	6.46 (6.61)	D
$Cu(C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4SCl)_2$	6.04 (6.08)	57.29 (57.33)	3.80 (3.82)	10.66 (10.70)	6.10 (6.12)	2.10
$Ni(C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4SCl)_2$	5.60 (5.64)	57.53 (57.60)	3.82 (3.84)	10.73 (10.75)	6.09 (6.14)	D
$Co(C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4SCl)_2$	5.62 (5.65)	57.56 (57.59)	3.81 (3.84)	10.73 (10.75)	6.08 (6.14)	2.49
$Fe(C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4SCl.H_2O)_2$	5.15 (5.20)	55.77 (55.82)	4.04 (4.09)	10.39 (10.42)	5.91 (5.95)	D
$C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2Cl$	—	53.66 (53.71)	3.38 (3.42)	8.92 (8.96)	13.61 (13.66)	D
$Cu(C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2Cl)_2$	6.33 (6.35)	52.76 (52.77)	2.96 (2.99)	8.38 (8.40)	12.73 (12.79)	2.08
$Ni(C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2Cl)_2$	5.88 (5.90)	53.00 (53.02)	2.99 (3.01)	8.41 (8.44)	12.83 (12.66)	D
$Co(C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2Cl)_2$	5.91 (5.93)	53.00 (53.01)	3.00 (3.01)	8.42 (8.44)	12.84 (12.86)	2.44
$Fe(C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2Cl.H_2O)_2$	5.40 (5.43)	51.30 (51.32)	3.26 (3.30)	8.24 (8.26)	12.40 (12.44)	D

D=Diamagnetic.

(i) 0.8 ml nitric acid (1.0 M) + 11.2 ml water + 24.0 ml dioxane + 4.0 ml potassium nitrate (1.0 M),

(ii) 0.8 ml nitric acid (1.0 M) + 11.2 ml water + 22.0 ml dioxane + 2.0 ml ligands (0.1 M) + 4.0 ml potassium nitrate (1.0 M), and

(iii) 0.8 ml nitric acid (1.0 M) + 11.2 ml water + 22.0 ml dioxane + 2.0 ml ligands (0.1 M) + 0.4 ml metal ion solution (0.1 M) + 4.0 ml potassium nitrate (1.0 M).

In each case total volume was made upto 40 ml by adding required amount of double distilled water or purified dioxane as the case may be.

The ionic strength was maintained by adding appropriate amount of potassium nitrate solution (0.1 M). The mixtures were titrated with standard KOH solution. A modified form of Irving-Rossotti³ titration technique was used for calculating the stability constants. The pH meter was calibrated with aqueous buffers. In the calculations for pL, the pH meter reading 'B' was used instead of converting it to true pH value (corresponding to aqueous medium). The use of pH meter reading 'B' instead of true pH values did not make any difference^{3,4} in the calculation of free ligand concentration and was usually valid for water dioxane media.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The analytical data of the Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Fe^{II} chelates (Table 1) show that they

are of the type ML_2 . In case of iron(II) complexes, TGA study shows the presence of two co-ordinated water molecules. Their electrical conductance measurements in DMF ($3-6 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) show that they are non ionic.

Magnetic moments: The room temperature magnetic moment show that the Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic while the Co^{II} complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.30-2.5$ B.M.) showing square planar geometry around the metal ions. The higher magnetic moments of Cu^{II} complexes (2.05-2.10 B.M.) as compared to spin only values is presumably due to spin-orbit coupling. The diamagnetism of Fe^{II} complexes show that they are octahedral (low-spin).

UV and visible spectra: For the square planar copper complexes (D_4h) three absorption bands are expected corresponding to ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{1g}$, ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$. In the present case, only two absorption bands are obtained at 15630-16130 and 13330-13520 cm^{-1} and are attributed to the transitions ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$, respectively. The ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ band would have overlapped with ${}^1B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ band and so it could not be seen in the spectra. However, their spectral data support the square planar geometry of the copper chelates. The diamagnetic nickel chelates show two absorption bands at 14290-14710 cm^{-1} and 17240-17850 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_{1g}$ transitions, respectively and supporting the square planar configuration of nickel chelates. The paramagnetic

cobalt chelates show two broad diffused bands one at 18870-19230 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition and at 15380-16130 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transition indicating their square planar structure.

The iron chelates show a very broad diffused band at 15160-15380 cm^{-1} showing octahedral structure.

Infrared spectra : The ligands shows bands around 3150-3060 cm^{-1} (OH) of the intramolecular

hydrogen bonded $\text{O} \cdots \text{O}$ group. This band is absent in the complexes indicating the breaking of the hydrogen bonding and consequent deprotonation and coordination of the metal ion. The band at 1640-1650 cm^{-1} (C=N) of the ligands undergoes a negative shift in the complexes indicating nitrogen coordination of the azomethine moiety⁷. The occurrence of medium intensity band at 3240-3420 cm^{-1} in iron chelates and its absence in other chelates show that the iron chelates have coordinated water molecules unlike the others.

Potentiometric study : The pH metric study of the metal chelates shows the \bar{n} values as 1.8, indicating two ligands per metal ion. The stepwise stability constants (Table 2) follow the Irving-Williams order.

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TABLE 2—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR METAL CHELATES IN 60% (v/v) DIOXANE

Constant	$\mu = 0.1 M$; Temp. $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$		
	SNOHB	STOHB	SDCHB
H			
$\log K_1^H$	10.65	11.58	11.24
Cu ^{II}			
$\log K_1$	8.38	7.99	8.11
$\log K_2$	6.62	6.08	6.45
$\log \beta_2$	15.00	14.02	14.56
Ni ^{II}			
$\log K_1$	7.98	7.70	7.82
$\log K_2$	6.57	5.88	6.24
$\log \beta_2$	14.55	13.58	14.06
Co ^{II}			
$\log K_1$	7.91	7.63	7.73
$\log K_2$	6.21	5.78	6.54
$\log \beta_2$	14.12	13.41	14.27
Fe ^{II}			
$\log K_1$	7.45	7.44	7.58
$\log K_2$	6.33	5.64	6.16
$\log \beta_2$	13.78	13.08	14.74